

A framework for positive action in research funding and careers

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Introduction

Building on the University of Oxford's work on [Equity in Research Funding](#), this framework and guidance has been produced by a cross-sector working group which forms part of the Equity in Research Funding Forum. The Forum brings together research organisations and funders to focus on equity in the context of research funding, specifically seeking opportunities to work in collaboration to make a positive difference.

For the purposes of this resource, 'research funding' includes funding awarded to individuals or teams undertaking research. This includes funding for doctoral studentships, Fellowships and any other funding which supports the delivery of research, including funding awarded internally within research organisations. This framework also explores how underrepresentation in associated career development can be addressed through positive action, as equity in research is interdependent with having a more diverse researcher population generally.

This framework is for those responsible for the approval, design, implementation and evaluation of research funding schemes and associated initiatives within research funders and research organisations.

Aims

The aims of the Positive Action in Research Framework are:

1. To provide a supportive resource focusing on potential positive action interventions related to research funding, and research careers, showcasing case studies which demonstrate positive action in practice.
2. To empower practitioners across the research ecosystem to advocate for positive action within research funding, and design and implement effective interventions.

Principles

Since positive action can sometimes be misunderstood, perceived as divisive, and be harmful if applied incorrectly, the priority group identified a set of underpinning principles which we believe are important for progressing understanding and engagement with positive action. These principles are:

Integrity

Positive action must be approached with integrity, rigour and care. Poorly designed and implemented positive action can have the potential to create as much harm as benefit.

Adding value

Positive action must genuinely add measurable value for researchers in marginalised groups and those working to increase equity in research funding.

Transparency

Positive action should be undertaken transparently to help ensure trust in processes and outcomes.

Not using a deficit model

Great care should be taken to ensure that positive action interventions do not rely on or perpetuate a deficit model (i.e. a perspective that attributes failures or shortcomings to individual deficiencies rather than systemic issues or external factors).

Taking an evidence-informed approach

Those designing and implementing positive action should always review and reflect on all available evidence to inform their approaches and make clear what evidence has been used. Data should be regularly reviewed to ensure there is a continuing need for each positive action initiative.

Incorporating clear evaluation approaches

Positive action interventions should be carefully and regularly evaluated, ensuring that any adverse impacts are addressed swiftly.

Legal compliance

Robust positive action measures may present legal risks, but for the benefit of the whole sector, these need to be approached responsibly.

Positive Action in Research Funding Framework

How to use this framework

This framework is designed to support confidence and considered approaches for policy makers, project leads and practitioners to develop and deliver positive action initiatives in research funding. It covers four main areas, providing guidance, prompts and examples to support research funders and research organisations to explore positive action and how to put initiatives into practice.

Photo credit: Paul Dodds

The main sections of the framework can be summarised as follows:

Why Positive Action?

This section outlines what positive action is, and the circumstances in which it can be considered, with a focus on the research funding context.

A Robust Approach

This section provides guidance and supportive prompts to ensure positive action initiatives are robust and fit for purpose.

Positive Action in Research Funding Framework

Making the Case

This section outlines likely objections and counterarguments, and risks and mitigations, to help support a case for positive action.

Positive Action in Practice

This section provides a list of potential positive action initiatives relevant to research funding and provides some case studies of positive action initiatives in practice.

What is Positive Action?

Positive action involves taking proportionate steps to lessen disadvantages or remove barriers and obstacles that can reasonably be believed are faced by people who share a protected characteristic.

Positive action measures were adopted in the Equality Act 2010 (the 'Act') in acknowledgement that anti-discrimination legislation, based on the principle of equal treatment, by itself might not be sufficient for tackling the historical disadvantage, systemic bias and more subtle forms of discrimination faced by some groups. It is a complementary legislative tool designed to help address these issues and create a level playing field for protected groups.

There are two provisions in the Act that enable positive action:

Section 158 permits the use of positive action measures to alleviate disadvantage experienced by people who share a protected characteristic, reduce their under-representation in relation to particular activities, and meet their particular needs. It will, for example, allow measures to be targeted to particular groups, including training to enable them to gain employment, or services to address their needs. Any such measures must be a proportionate way of achieving the relevant aim.

The extent to which it is proportionate to take positive action measures which may result in people not having the relevant characteristic being treated less favourably will depend, among other things, on the seriousness of the relevant disadvantage, the extremity of need or under-representation and the availability of other means of countering them.

Section 159 permits an employer to take a protected characteristic into consideration when deciding whom to recruit or promote, where people having the protected characteristic are at a disadvantage or are under-represented. This can be done only where the candidates are as qualified as each other. The question of whether one person is as qualified as another is not a matter only of academic qualification, but rather a judgement based on the criteria the employer uses to establish who is best for the job which could include matters such as suitability, competence and professional performance.

The provision does not allow employers to have a policy or practice of automatically treating people who share a protected characteristic more favourably than those who do not have it in these circumstances; each case must be considered on its merits. Any action taken must be a proportionate means of addressing such disadvantage or under-representation. Section 159 is commonly referred to as the 'tie-break' provision.

Why Positive Action?

The University of Oxford's report, [‘Equity and Inclusivity in Research Funding: Barriers and Delivering Change’](#) identifies eight key barriers to securing research funding for marginalised researchers: inaccessibility, vulnerability to bias, failure to account for structural inequality, reliance on third-party support, assessing against irrelevant characteristics, limited experience of EDI issues, lack of clear and transparent information and increased burden on marginalised researchers. The report notes the way in which these factors interact with and at times, exacerbate each other.

Positive action approaches have the potential to mitigate some of these barriers.

“ When applying for a substantial grant from the Royal Academy of Engineering, I was able to use their “access mentoring scheme”, which provided me with a mentor who had successfully applied to the same grant. At the time, I was working from home a lot because of the challenges of childcare during the pandemic, and I was finding it difficult to access help and advice from my workplace. My RAEng mentor helped me to fine tune key parts of my application to the requirements of the scheme and gave me confidence that I could communicate my ideas in a way that made sense to people outside of my field. I was successful in winning the grant and also felt that the overall experience had improved my skills and confidence, partly because of the advice I had from my mentor. ”

Rachel Oliver, Professor of Materials Science, University of Cambridge

Photo credit: Paul Dodds

A Robust Approach

There is limited case law on positive action, and it can be difficult to define legal positive action, so it is important to approach it through robust processes. This means gathering an effective evidence base and giving due consideration to what a proportionate measure would be (ie something that addresses the evidenced need). Proportionality is key when designing positive action initiatives.

Important points to consider:

- Has a robust process been followed to develop this initiative?
- Has an effective evidence base been gathered?
- Is the proposed activity proportional to meet the evidenced need?
- Does it include savings clauses (an element of discretion to include people experiencing the same disadvantage who are not from the specified protected characteristic) and sunset clauses (that it will be reviewed)?

The framework provides examples of the sorts of interventions that have been used in the sector to address specific needs – this is supported by the case studies later in this framework which include details about the design process and impacts of the work.

Making the Case for Positive Action

Positive action initiatives can meet with resistance.

Objections and Counterarguments

It is helpful to be aware of likely objections to positive action, so that counterarguments can be prepared. Noon¹ (2011) and Manfredi (2017) identify a range of common objections to implementing positive action and set out clear counterarguments.

These can be summarised as follows:

Objection: Undermining of meritocracy

This objection is based on the idea that those with the most merit should be rewarded and be supported to succeed.

One counterargument to this is that merit may not be ‘as value neutral as it might first appear’ (Noon, 2011) – for example, is it about talent and potential, effort and achievement, success against the odds? How can these things be measured?

Manfredi suggests an argument that positive action is in fact a mechanism to ensure that meritocracy is truly implemented – using the illustrative example of the underrepresentation of women in senior leadership roles at universities despite good representation in lower-level roles. Assuming talent is equally distributed across men and women, this suggests that meritocracy as it currently operates is in fact ‘dysfunctional’ (Manfredi, 2017).

Positive Action at the Wellcome Sanger Institute – Excellence Fellowships and Returners Scheme

The Wellcome Sanger Institute, a globally recognised genomics research centre, has developed innovative positive action programmes to address structural barriers and improve diversity in research careers.

The three-year Sanger Excellence Fellowships are targeted at researchers from Black heritage backgrounds.² The programme aims to attract outstanding talent while supporting Fellows through tailored training, mentorship, and career development opportunities. By investing in long-term progression, the scheme helps build a more diverse and sustainable future research pipeline.

A key strength of the programme is its holistic approach. The Institute worked in partnership with grassroots community organisations to co design and deliver interventions, ensuring they were relevant and impactful.

Recruitment practices were also redesigned to be more inclusive, including the use of narrative CVs that allow applicants to demonstrate a broader range of experiences and potential. Senior leaders actively supported workshops and engagement activities, reinforcing institutional commitment to culture change.

The Institute has also prioritised transparency by sharing evaluation findings and recommendations, contributing to wider sector learning.

Complementing this, a Returners Scheme supports postdoctoral researchers returning after extended leave, such as parental or caring responsibilities. By recognising the impact of disruptions on career progression and providing targeted support, the scheme helps retain talented researchers and promotes a more inclusive research environment.³

² www.sanger.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/Excellence-Fellowship-summary-report-Feb-2023-final.pdf

³ <https://sangerinstitute.blog/2023/06/06/new-scheme-launched-to-support-researchers-returning-after-extended-leave/>

¹ Noon’s paper uses the term ‘positive discrimination’ - which this framework does not advocate for. However, the moral, political and philosophical objections can be similar to positive action.

Objection: Failure to select the ‘best’ candidate

This objection stems from the idea that a less-qualified candidate with a certain protected characteristic could be selected for an opportunity over a more-qualified candidate without that characteristic.

Here it is key to point towards the Equality Act which clearly states that section 159 (described above) can only be applied where candidates are as qualified as each other. The sections of the Equality Act summarised above allow for positive action in favour of a candidate from an underrepresented group where either a) there is a tie-break between two equally qualified candidates or b) where multiple candidates meet a threshold for being able to perform the job.

Objection: Negative impact on beneficiaries

This objection is one which sometimes comes from potential beneficiaries of positive action as well as others arguing against it – essentially arguing that being a beneficiary of positive action could result in them, or other colleagues with the same characteristic(s) being seen as deficient in some way.

Noon (2011) urges ‘caution in assuming that beneficiaries will reject positive discrimination’, noting that there is no evidence to suggest this is a widespread view. A key counterargument here is that by doing nothing, the disadvantage will continue. Approaching the development of positive action measures through a robust process should mitigate for potential negative impacts on beneficiaries.

Objection: Positive action is unjust

This argument is that taking action in support of underrepresented groups is essentially discriminating against majority groups, and just as bad as discriminating against the underrepresented groups.

When counterarguing this point, it can be useful to articulate equality as a means of ‘breaking cycles of disadvantage’ (Manfredi, 2017), framing positive action within a broader commitment to social inclusion rather than preferential treatment. Lawful positive action is designed to address evidenced structural barriers, not to replace one form of unfairness with another.

“ The use of positive action, far from trying to remedy an injustice with another injustice, should be seen as a tool to correct existing injustice. ”

Manfredi, 2017

It can also help to acknowledge that, where systems have historically advantaged majority groups, efforts to correct these imbalances may be experienced by some as a loss or as unfair. Recognising this perception—without accepting its premise—can be an important step in constructive dialogue and effective communication about why positive action is both lawful and necessary.

Objection: Positive action doesn’t guarantee culture change

It could be argued that ‘artificially’ inflating representation of minoritised groups in research isn’t sufficient to change culture.

The counter to this is that increasing representation is a starting point. In addressing this objection, it can be helpful to consider how the proposed positive action initiative fits in with broader work to develop inclusive research cultures.

Manfredi also specifically articulates the potential for objections linked to legal risks, which are explored in more detail in the next section.

Beyond the objections explored here, positive action can prompt a range of responses, some of which highlight genuine risks or implementation challenges. Acknowledging and engaging with these perspectives is important: constructive criticism can reveal practical issues, help refine proposed measures, and ensure that actions are proportionate, legally robust, and aligned with actual barriers experienced by underrepresented groups.

Further objections may be rooted in prejudicial views about specific groups and their innate abilities or suitability for particular types of work. Where these views are expressed, it is important to challenge and support reflection on the biases which inform them.

A Risk-Informed Approach to Positive Action

To effectively make a case for positive action within an institution, it is helpful to be able to articulate the risks associated with specific activities along with appropriate mitigations – but also, importantly, to be able to explain the risks of not engaging with positive action.

Understanding and Mitigating Risks in Positive Action

This Framework advocates for both courageous and conscientious effort on positive action in research funding, in equal measure. In addition to legal risks, there is a broader framework of risks that must be considered and addressed for interventions to be successful. These are articulated below, along with proposed mitigations.

Risk of Inertia

There is a significant risk of not doing anything when data and evidence clearly indicate inequity in research funding processes. Inaction can undermine organisational credibility and signal a lack of commitment to research excellence, particularly as funders, regulators and the wider sector increasingly expect demonstrable progress on equity. Failure to act may also constrain the future talent pipeline and limit the diversity of ideas that underpin high-quality research.

Mitigations

To reduce this risk, organisations should ensure:

- Clear alignment between proposed positive action initiatives and institutional values, strategic priorities and commitments to research excellence.
- Defined governance and ownership, so that responsibility for progressing actions is explicit and supported by senior leaders.
- Robust evaluation plans and a timeline for reviewing impact, allowing for iterative improvement rather than stalling through uncertainty or caution.

Positive Action through Applicant Mentoring and a Guaranteed Interview Scheme

The Nottingham BBSRC Doctoral Training Partnership (DTP) identified a persistent lack of ethnic diversity in its PhD recruitment, with only 0–6% of students from racially minoritised backgrounds between 2012 and 2019. Initial inclusive recruitment changes—such as improved marketing, anonymised applications, and revised selection criteria—representation of racially minoritised postgraduate researchers to 11.4% in 2020. However, Black and Black mixed applicants remained underrepresented.

To address this, the DTP co-developed two targeted positive action initiatives with current students: the Amplify mentoring programme and a guaranteed interview scheme. Amplify offers tailored support to Black and Black mixed applicants through one-to-one mentoring, application guidance, interview preparation, and campus visits. Mentors are trained postgraduate researchers, ensuring applicants receive informed and supportive guidance.

The guaranteed interview scheme allows Black and Black mixed applicants who hold or expect to hold a 2.1 degree in a relevant subject, or equivalent qualification to opt in for an interview, helping to remove barriers in the selection process.

These interventions had a significant impact. In 2021, representation of UK postgraduate researchers from racially minoritised backgrounds rose to 23.7%, with Black students making up 15.8% of the cohort. Importantly, some successful candidates would not have progressed without these measures.

The DTP continues to refine its approach, aiming for at least 20% racially minoritised postgraduate researchers in future cohorts.⁴

⁴ www.nottingham.ac.uk/edi/documents/uon-edi-pgr-recruitment-guide-accesspdf.pdf

Legal and Financial Risk

Firstly, it is important to note that unless a measure is positive action under the Equality Act 2010, it is unlawful discrimination in the UK and would run counter to the principles of this Framework. “Positive discrimination” is a misnomer with no place in law, but is often used to describe discrimination that is purportedly used as a means to correct inequality but does not meet the requirements for lawful positive action. Such measures are unlawful direct discrimination under the Equality Act 2010.

Through our Working Group, we explored how a common impediment to positive action can be internal legal advice either urging severe caution or advising against initiatives completely, which is understandable since it is the role of in-house legal teams, or externally sourced advice, to protect the organisation from litigation. For practitioners and policymakers designing positive action interventions, this can occasionally be perceived as ‘gatekeeping’. Ultimately, the risk appetite for how bold the organisation should be in its pursuit of equity, diversity and inclusion is the responsibility of senior leadership, taking into account a range of factors, including legal advice, and also the financial and reputational risks of ‘getting it wrong’.

Mitigations

- All positive action measures must be taken in accordance with the Equality Act. Where there are understood to be ‘grey areas’ and areas of ambiguity, senior leaders should make final decisions on the viability of riskier positive action interventions going ahead.
- All those involved in designing and operating positive action interventions should be knowledgeable about the legal framework, and the parameters and limits of it.
- Establishing mutually positive and supportive relationships between Legal Teams and practitioners / policy-makers is important, providing early sight of proposals for advice and buy-in.
- Robust Equality Impact Assessments should set out the rationale and evidence-base for positive action, also summarising risks and mitigations.
- To evidence that positive action is proportionate and legitimate, it should be demonstrated that it is one of a series of interventions that have been attempted to address the underrepresentation or disadvantage at stake.
- All parties involved with creating and operating positive action should understand cautionary cases from employment law on when positive action has been judged to be unlawful, and why, for example:

Furlong v Chief Constable of Cheshire Police

In this case, the police used a recruitment process where all candidates who passed initial stages were treated as equally qualified. They then favoured candidates from underrepresented groups in the decision-making process. This practice was found to be unlawful at employment tribunal because it went beyond the permissible scope of positive action under the Equality Act 2010, as it did not provide enough distinction between all of the candidates in the initial stages of the process.

Richardson v York & Scarborough Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust

In this case, a white healthcare assistant, brought a claim against York and Scarborough Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, alleging racial discrimination over a leadership programme aimed at Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BME) staff. The programme was introduced in response to NHS Workforce Race Equality Standard (WRES) data showing under-representation of minority ethnic staff in leadership roles.

The complainant argued the initiative was divisive and excluded white employees, creating unlawful positive discrimination. Although she did not apply for the course, she felt disadvantaged by its framing and raised a formal grievance.

The tribunal found the complainant had been treated less favourably because the course appeared to exclude white staff. However, it ruled that this did not amount to unlawful discrimination. The Trust’s actions were deemed lawful positive action under the Equality Act 2010, aimed at addressing inequality.

The claim was dismissed, with the tribunal noting that clearer communication could have prevented misunderstanding.

Organisational Bureaucracy

Universities and research institutes may be particularly prone to bureaucracy and complexity, due to high levels of regulatory and compliance requirements, decentralised structures operating semi-independently, and complex stakeholder needs and cultures where individual autonomy in decision making is highly valued. All of these factors, and more, can make it challenging to implement politically, reputationally and legally sensitive measures such as positive action.

Mitigations

- The complexity of working across different parts of the organisation to implement larger-scale positive action initiatives can often be experienced as an attitudinal barrier, rather than a practical one. Designing and implementing positive action usually requires collaboration and teamwork. Having a well-positioned senior sponsor for the intervention can help overcome silos and systemic obstacles.
- Robust oversight and reporting through established governance routes is critical.
- Making explicit decisions about risk appetite, and reflecting these in governance and process design, can help to reduce bureaucratic inertia.

Reputational Risks

In addition to the external reputational risk that litigation can bring to an organisation, poorly conceived and implemented positive action can have negative consequences on the reputation of leaders, managers, practitioners and policymakers internally. This further impacts on wellbeing, and risks undermining the credibility of individuals that are recipients of the intervention and harming their reputations and wellbeing too.

Mitigations

- Senior leadership messaging, showing how positive action interventions are linked to broader organisational strategies, missions and values on improving quality in research is important (with diversity and inclusion being an important aspect of excellence in research).
- Reactive communications should be pre-planned and ready, in the event of complaints or backlash, with agreement of who will be the accountable senior manager to lead on such a response if required.

Risk of Backlash

Poor levels of understanding of the difference between positive action, and positive discrimination, alongside poorly implemented or communicated interventions, can create the risk of backlash. Backlash can stem from perceptions of unfairness if it is seen that decisions are being taken based on protected characteristics, rather than skill and experience, and this can be even more acute at times when competition for research funding is intense, and resources scarcer. Recipients of positive action interventions can also be the targets of such backlash, through the perception of unjust preferential treatment. In turn, this can lead to some groups and individuals de-selecting themselves from positive action opportunities.

Mitigations

- The purpose, scope and justification for the positive action should be well articulated to all stakeholders throughout the design, implementation, and evaluation of the measures. It should not be pre-supposed that everybody will be bought into it or understand it.
- There should be full transparency around selection criteria, and awarding thresholds, for positive action, clearly evidencing how there will be no reduction in quality or lowering of standards, and selection is merit-based.
- Positive action should be co-designed with its intended recipients/targets, with consideration about the potential for backlash built-in to the co design process from the outset.

- Having very senior, respected allies with lived experience of discrimination and disadvantage speak openly about their experiences can be a powerful counter-mechanism.

Risks to the wider sector

Confidence in positive action in the wider higher education and research sectors is variable, with some organisations being more risk-averse than others, and this likely being associated with leadership commitment and direction on EDI more generally. Poorly designed and implemented positive action interventions risk harming progress and programmes across the sector, by increasing the likelihood of litigation, and in turn intensifying the possibility of wider risk aversion. In addition, the wider political landscape, especially emanating from, but not confined to, the US, and the targeting of EDI in polarising debates, is leading to an erosion over time in the desirability of undertaking more interventionist measures, such as positive action.

Mitigations

- Each organisation needs to demonstrate its own process of due diligence on positive action measures and should not rely solely on precedents set by others.

Risk of Ineffectiveness

Positive action can be emotive in nature, as the drivers are usually societal and evoke strong sentiments. This can make it feel distinct from other change initiatives, and risks positioning it outside of standard strategic change approaches. This may also be potentially linked to how the EDI function is positioned and regarded within the organisation. Poorly designed and implemented positive action risks being ineffective, and not delivering on the outcomes anticipated, which in turn can lead to loss of trust from all concerned, low morale and cynicism about the ability to make progress on EDI.

Mitigations

In the design and implementation of positive action measures, the same rigour, standards and principles used in any project management / strategic change initiative should be applied, for example:

- Need for appropriate baseline data
- Success metrics and evaluation plans
- Co-creation with relevant groups
- Clear ownership and resource allocation

Positive Action in Practice

Types of Initiative

“ The Royal Academy of Engineering is committed to taking positive action in its research funding. Positive action is an essential tool in addressing structural inequalities and ensuring equitable access to opportunities. There is still deeply entrenched injustice in engineering and technology research and, as research funders, we need to be bold to address it. By removing barriers and widening participation, we can enable the full breadth of engineering talent to drive excellence, innovation, and impact. ”

Royal Academy of Engineering

The table below presents some suggested activities which could be used as part of positive action initiatives. These range in scale, cost (financial and resource), likely impact and potential risk level and are intended to be an illustrative, rather than comprehensive, list, which will aid exploration of potential initiatives.

Some of these initiatives may carry different levels of legal, financial or reputational risk depending on how they are designed and implemented. They should always be considered in light of the legal framework and organisational context.

Type of Intervention	Interventions	What might this look like?
Structural and Procedural	Application Quotas	Allowing two applications per institution, but up to four as long as two of the applications are from candidates from a specific minoritised group.
	Positive Action in Shortlisting	Including candidates from minoritised groups in shortlists where their scoring places them just below the normal cut-off point.
	Positive Action Statements	Including a statement encouraging applicants from minoritised groups to apply in your funding call. This should be a targeted statement which reflects specific areas of underrepresentation in applicants to the scheme or the discipline.
Targeted Funding	Scholarships/Fellowships	Targeted scholarships or fellowships for specified minoritised groups.
	Research Internships	Targeted research internship programmes for minoritised undergraduates, designed to support progression in research careers.
	Bridging Funding	Prioritised bridging funding for researchers from minoritised groups who have secured funding, but with a gap between current and subsequent funding. Bridging funding would cover the gap, allowing for continuity of contract.
	Internal Funds	This could include targeted calls for minoritised groups for professional development or research activity.
	Conference/Travel Care Funds	Providing access to additional funding for conference attendance and/or travel for researchers who have caring commitments.
	In-grant Inclusion Budgets	Specifically allowing applicants to cost in additional costs related to inclusion – for example, childcare costs. Guidance for reviewers should also explain that this should not negatively impact the assessment of value for money.
Targeted Support Activities	Network Engagement Support	Providing support (financial, time) for candidates from minoritised groups to engage with targeted networks for researchers from similar backgrounds.
	Coaching	Providing targeted coaching opportunities.
	Mentoring	Providing targeted mentoring opportunities.
	Events	Developing events or supporting attendance at events which support minoritised groups to build professional networks.
	Training	Developing specific training offerings targeting minoritised groups or providing targeted support for researchers from minoritised groups to access training.

Case Studies

Case Study 1: Wellcome – Accelerator Awards

Organisation: Wellcome

Summary

The Wellcome Accelerator Award scheme supports researchers of Black, Bangladeshi and Pakistani heritage in the UK to undertake activities that strengthen their position to reach the next career stage in academia. The funding can be used for research or research-adjacent activities.

Grants provide up to two years of flexible funding (including salary support and up to £200,000 in project costs) and can be used for a wide range of activities such as pilot research, secondments, writing time, training or network-building.

The scheme focuses on addressing the persistent underrepresentation of researchers from specific groups in the UK research sector by providing greater equity of opportunity within the research funding landscape.

The initiative combines:

- Targeted funding specifically for eligible researchers.
- Community strengthening activities to support peer networks and build collective capacity.

The Evidence Base

To evidence that the intervention is proportionate and meets a legitimate aim, Wellcome began by analysing their own data on grant applications and success rates by ethnicity, which showed variable trends. They then analysed HESA's national research population data and found clear and persistent evidence of underrepresentation of Black, Bangladeshi and Pakistani heritage researchers compared to broader population census data. They further undertook a desktop review of other similar schemes from comparable organisations to understand their impact.

Intervention Design and Buy-In

Focus groups were held with the target communities to better understand the barriers they faced in their research careers, which helped inform the design of the intervention.

A governance structure was created to ensure that all key stakeholders had input and oversight of the programme: membership included representation from communications, finance, legal, the research funding division, and so forth. This formed the basis of an interim EDI Committee, which then evolved into a full committee responsible for the organisation's broader commitments and actions on EDI, mainstreaming and supplementing positive action initiatives.

The Accelerator Award programme received formal endorsement from Wellcome's Executive team, ensuring support from the most senior levels.

The scheme was then launched and promoted through the widest possible channels, including social media platforms, university funding boards, and research consortia.

Overcoming Challenges

To mitigate reputational risks, communications were carefully managed to avoid framing the scheme as addressing "deficient" researchers. Instead, messaging focused on structural racism and systemic barriers. Clear explanations were provided as to why these specific groups were targeted, with reference to evidence of underrepresentation.

Legal risks were managed by having strong, evidence-based data for the intervention, supported by external, expert professional advice.

Whilst some criticism of the programme was received, mainly concerning accusations of positive discrimination and reverse racism, this was not as voluminous as anticipated and was addressed through the transparent sharing of data and evidence to demonstrate that the intervention was proportionate and legitimate.

A key challenge was operational pressures and the need to embed the scheme within existing workloads, which initially required significant additional staff time and resources.

Outcomes and Impact

Engagement and applications for the scheme were high. Due to strong demand, the eligibility criteria for round 2 were revised to focus more explicitly on early- and mid-career researchers. So far, across two rounds, 65 researchers have been successfully granted Accelerator Awards and are receiving not just financial support but also strengthened professional confidence, visibility, and longer-term competitiveness.

As a relatively new intervention, longer-term impacts (such as progression to larger grants) are still being tracked.

Insights and Advice

Wellcome's overarching advice to organisations considering positive action to address inequity in research funding is to "not let fear of backlash hold you back from action that you know is right."

Case Study 2: Lancaster University – Increasing Diversity in Impact Acceleration Funding

Organisation: Lancaster University

Context and Rationale

Impact Acceleration Accounts (IAA) are strategic awards provided by UKRI and its associated research councils to research organisations, to be used creatively for a wide range of impact and engagement activities.

Individual institutions have autonomy over how best to deploy the funding, being required to support activities and projects which enable external organisations and partners to apply research into their products, services, practices, or industrial applications. Lancaster University received ~£3m across the Engineering and Physical Sciences and Arts and Humanities disciplines, to be distributed internally over five years.

Through a series of small, targeted, positive action interventions, the University aimed to address the underrepresentation of specific groups in its IAA-funded programmes.

The Evidence Base

Equality Impact Assessments (EIA) undertaken by the University revealed underrepresentation in IAA-funded programmes, particularly among:

- Women
- Disabled researchers
- Researchers from ethnic groups other than white

- Early Career Researchers (ECRs)

This data informed the target groups to which the positive action would be directed.

Intervention Design and Buy-In

UKRI's agenda to advance diversity in grant awards and participation helped influence the University's approach to improving inclusive practice in allocating IAA-funded programmes.

An analysis of the EIA data, evidencing underrepresentation in IAA internal grant awards among specific groups, was presented to the programme's Executive Board, who were supportive of efforts to address it.

The range of positive action measures subsequently put in place included:

- Positive action statements included within subsequent funding calls.
- Transparent acknowledgement of underrepresentation in funding documentation.
- Targeted promotion of calls via relevant staff networks.
- A sandpit-style event specifically encouraging ECR participation to foster partnerships with external stakeholders.

- Pre-application webinars to provide clarity on the programme and application process.
- Light-touch, low-risk processes to reduce barriers to participation.

Overcoming Challenges

No significant procedural challenges arose as the existing panel review process remained unchanged. However, supporting ECR engagement required additional encouragement and guidance, reflecting the higher level of support often needed at earlier career stages.

Outcomes and Impact

Following the interventions, an updated EIA analysis demonstrated improved diversity across most areas of the programme, with some areas highlighted as requiring more focused work and continued interventions. For example, the rate of successful female applicants for EPSRC grants improved by 8%, 11% for ethnic groups other than white, and 9% for those with a declared disability. The outcomes for AHRC grants were varied, with a 16% increase in successful female applicants, but reductions among applicants from ethnic groups other than white (-23%) and disabled applicants (-5%).

The targeted promotion and pre-application support appeared to improve both programme engagement and application quality.

Insights and Advice

Informal conversations with researchers from underrepresented groups that accompanied the interventions were particularly helpful, more clearly surfacing challenges such as “imposter syndrome” and misperceptions about the IAA programme itself.

Also, the programme leads were able to explain to researchers why it is always beneficial to engage with and express interest in the funding, as last-minute, unexpected opportunities may arise that could support projects. Overall, the interventions helped demystify how internal schemes operate and foster a more inclusive culture of engagement.

Case Study 3: University of Leeds – Research EDI (REDI) Fund

Organisation: University of Leeds

Summary

The University of Leeds Research EDI (REDI) fund aims to support career development activities that would enhance promotion prospects and, over time, increase the representation of underrepresented groups at senior academic and research levels.

Awards of up to £15,000 were available in Round 1 and £12,000 in Round 2. Applicants submitted a brief two-page proposal outlining their planned activities and how this would enhance their career impact.

The scheme targeted research academics (Grades 8 and 9) who self-identified as women and people of marginalised genders, people of minoritised ethnicities, and disabled people. The fund was also open to academics making a significant positive contribution to equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI), regardless of personal characteristics.

The Evidence Base

Statistical data on the University's academic and research workforce demonstrated a clear underrepresentation of women, minoritised ethnic groups, and disabled academics at Grades 8 and 9, relative to the overall academic population.

Intervention Design and Buy-in

Evaluation of existing positive action programmes at the University informed the approach of creating a flexible fund that could be used for a wide range of career-enhancing activities. Feedback from other schemes, both internally and at a neighbouring institution, indicated that this was the most effective way to utilise funding, rather than engaging academics in a narrow range of pre-determined activities that might not be suitable for their individual circumstances or career stage.

The scheme was driven by the Dean of Research Culture, who benefited from serving on many senior committees and thus had the credibility to gain support from other senior colleagues. The funding was already in place (via Research England), and institutions had autonomy over how best to strategically utilise it, so this removed any concerns about how the programme would be financed. This would have been the primary obstacle, had it not been for this.

Photo credit: Paul Dodds

Overcoming Challenges

The programme lead had open conversations with HR from the outset to explain the rationale for the intervention. Independent, professional, and impartial advice was sought, which provided confidence in the programme's design and legality, and that it was a proportionate means of achieving a legitimate aim.

The use of data enabled a scientific approach to building a solid argument, for example, through compelling "reality checks" that demonstrated how long it would take the institution to meet its EDI KPIs without robust positive action interventions.

Some staff questioned the exclusion of lower-grade academics, researchers, and professional services staff, or raised concerns that socio-economic disadvantage was not included.

Mitigations for this included:

- Clearly publishing the data-driven rationale for the scheme.
- Demonstrating that disparities were most significant at higher grades for the specified groups.
- Publishing detailed FAQs and expanding them as new queries arose.
- Providing tailored, courteous responses to individual concerns.
- Offering one-to-one meetings where appropriate to understand and address concerns.

Overall, transparency and consistent communication were central to maintaining trust in the programme's objectives, design, and implementation.

Intervention Features

Support was offered to applicants through online and in-person workshops.

The review and allocation process then used a partially randomised allocation process (lottery system). Firstly, a light-touch peer review was conducted to ensure that proposals met five core quality criteria. Applications meeting all criteria were then randomised. Intersectionality was recognised by increasing the weighting (e.g. multiple entries in the "lottery") for applicants eligible under more than one criterion. This approach balanced quality assurance with fairness, helping to reduce the influence of bias in final allocation decisions.

Successful applicants also accessed workshops on career development planning, promotion and progression, and professional profile enhancement.

Outcomes and Impact

There was a good conversion rate from engagement in the pre-application workshops to full application. Sixty-eight applications were made to the fund across two rounds, and 36 awards were made. In financial terms, £724k was requested, and £396k was awarded.

There was a lot of interest in understanding who had received the awards. The decision was taken not to publish the names of individuals to shield them from any potential backlash. This is because there was anecdotal evidence from other internal positive action programmes that recipients experienced resentment from their colleagues, based on the perception that positive action is unfair preferential treatment.

Feedback on the fund has been highly positive, particularly regarding the opportunity itself, the pre-application workshops, and the level of career development support provided. Seventy per cent of respondents to a qualitative evaluation survey reported that it enhanced their career prospects, and 50% of respondents confirmed that they intended to apply for promotion within the next two years.

It is too early to determine long-term effects on promotion outcomes. Given the nature of academic career progression, measurable impact on representation will likely take several years. Longitudinal tracking is planned.

Insights and Advice

The University of Leeds' advice on positive action is to be brave and work collectively with a wide range of stakeholders to ensure confidence in the intervention.

The University has further reflected on the necessity of undertaking foundational, systemic work on equity and fairness in research funding, as flagship positive action programmes alone do not fix structural issues.

Photo credit: Sam Sills, Whitedog Photography

Case Study 4: UCL's Women and Large Grant Leadership Programme

Summary

UCL's Women and Large Grant Leadership Programme was designed to address the gender disparity in research funding across many STEM disciplines. It took the form of a training programme targeted at mid- to established-career female academics, designed to equip this cohort with the skills, knowledge, support, and networks to successfully lead large grant applications.

The Evidence Base

Data from large funders such as Wellcome, EPSRC, and NERC show that women apply for fewer large grants than men and often have lower success rates. This was supplemented with analysis of UCL's own data, which showed a similar, albeit mixed, trend.

Intervention Design and Buy-in

The programme was initially designed and run for a cohort comprising three faculties: Engineering Sciences, the Built Environment, and Mathematical and Physical Sciences. Endorsement of the programme was provided by faculty leadership, based on data showing clear disparities in research funding for women, without requiring approval through formal governance routes. Financial support was provided by the three participating faculties to cover catering and to fund an external facilitator to supplement in-house expertise.

The second cohort was extended to additional faculties in Life and Medical Sciences and funded centrally by the Research Culture team.

Participants in the programme were selected through an open application process. The programme involved a high level of peer-to-peer support and learning. It consisted of informative presentations, discussions, and a masterclass on applying for large grants; a facilitated discussion on the barriers that women face; and an opportunity to pitch a large-grant vision and receive feedback from a senior academic panel. The programme was delivered over seven in-person sessions, with a total time commitment of around 14 hours.

Overcoming Challenges

A very small number of people queried the programme's targeting solely to women; however, these concerns were addressed by sharing data that showed differential outcomes in research funding by gender.

Concerns were also raised regarding the inclusive promotion of the programme to trans and non-binary staff, rather than basing it solely on biological sex. The programme leads were able to justify this on the grounds that the programme used the same eligibility criteria as other centrally run development programmes for women at the University.

Other challenges related to capacity—both for the research facilitators who designed and led the programme and for the participants. In the future, the programme leads will look to partner with other central teams to share the workload.

Outcomes and Impact

Fifty women have been trained through the programme over two cohorts. Many have fed back that they have since applied for large grants or fellowships that they would not have had the knowledge or confidence to pursue without the programme. A post-programme survey for cohort 2 found that:

- 94% strongly agreed or agreed that they improved their knowledge and understanding of developing large grant applications, with the rest being neutral.
- 67% strongly agreed or agreed that they have gained strategies for overcoming barriers, with the rest being neutral.

A full evaluation to assess the impact on successful large grant capture for the women involved in the programme is planned.

Insights and Advice

The advice from UCL echoes the themes and insights of this framework: positive action can be a useful supplementary tool to help level the playing field in research funding; however, it also requires leadership and systemic interventions to address deeply rooted inequalities.

A follow-on project, *Mind the Gender Funding Gap*, brought together alumnae from the programme and senior leaders across UCL to explore the persistent barriers women face when applying for research funding. The event focused on increasing senior leaders' understanding and awareness of their role in creating and maintaining more equitable research ecosystems. The event's output was a report summarising solutions and recommendations.

“ This pioneering programme which has transformed the way many of us work at UCL. Previously I had never written anything larger than a standard UKRI grant... The Women + Large Grants Training Programme was incredibly important in giving me the skills and confidence to put together a grant of this complexity. I learnt a great deal from my peers in the same cohort. ”

UCL Women Large Grant Leadership Programme Participant

Evaluation

Robust positive action initiatives are data-driven. The careful use of baseline data to inform the design of initiatives provides the foundation for meaningful evaluation (for example, the percentage of successful applicants from specific minoritised groups). Quantitative measures, however, are only one element of an effective evaluation plan.

Some questions to consider in developing an evaluation plan include:

- Has the initiative addressed or made positive progress against the problem it was designed to address?
- What can be evaluated at different stages of the initiative?
- When do we expect to see outputs, outcomes and longer-term impact?
- What was the scale of demand? Was this higher/lower than expected?
- How will you collect feedback from participants?
- What does feedback on the way the initiative was implemented tell you about participants' experiences?

- What challenges were encountered and how were these challenges addressed?
- Have any unintended consequences or perceptions emerged, and what can we learn from them?
- Were resources sufficient to deliver the initiative as planned?
- Is the initiative sustainable?

To support structured and values-led evaluation, organisations may find it helpful to draw on the principles of the International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) SCOPE framework. [The SCOPE model](#) provides a five-stage approach for designing evaluation processes that are proportionate, ethical and aligned to organisational values.

The Sanger Institute commissioned an evaluation of [the Sanger Excellence Fellowship](#), which provides a helpful example of evaluation of positive action in practice.

Early Career Interventions

UCL's Research Opportunity Scholarships (ROS) for Black and Asian postgraduate research students includes UK/home rate tuition fees, a maintenance stipend, a professional development package, and a single £1,000 allowance towards conference costs over the duration of the programme. The scholarships have supported 41 ROS scholars since 2019, and the conference fund has been used by the scholars to cover registration fees, travel and accommodation for national and international conferences, as well as equipment to enable students to create outputs for conference presentation.

B-Mentor Academic is a cross-institutional mentoring scheme for early-career academics, which has been running for over 10 years. Led by UCL, with six partnering London Universities, the scheme pairs early career academics who are racially minoritised as Black, Asian, Mixed and minority ethnic with senior academics to cultivate cross-institutional relationships, strengthen their skills, demystify formal and informal HE structures and build skills/knowledge on a range of topics including grant writing, professional development and promotions.

Underpinning inclusive practice

A clear theme arising from the development of this framework has been the need for underpinning inclusive practice and universal design – things that should be considered baseline good practice, regardless of whether targeted positive action is in place.

Ensuring that processes adhere to broad inclusive practice helps to build a stronger foundation for any targeted positive action and helps to create an environment in which positive action initiatives can prove successful. Ensuring that Equality Impact Assessment is a core element of funding process design can support this, and some of the key areas for consideration may include:

Process and Policy Design

- Inclusive criteria-setting
- Standardised data collection
- Use of narrative CVs
- Providing scope for extenuating circumstances to be considered within applications
- Co-creation of calls
- Allowing researchers to self-identify their career stage
- Timing of opportunities

Training and Capacity Building

- Reviewer training
- Flexible access to training opportunities (eg asynchronous approaches to training delivery)

Representation and Diversity

- Visibility of diverse role models (eg via case studies)
- Diverse decision-making panels
- Encouragement of inclusion of ECRs in research teams and supervisory teams
- Cultural awareness

Accessibility

- Language
- Documents and websites
- Physical spaces

Communication and Engagement

- Consistent and effective communications
- Wellbeing support

Our Approach

The working group has met monthly online and came together for an in-person co-creation workshop to allow for more detailed working. The draft framework was shared within the working group and more widely in the sector for feedback, with feedback reflected in the final version.

While we take a risk-based approach to support organisations to explore positive action, it is important to note that there is a significant risk of not taking positive action to address inequity in our funding system.

In developing this framework, we have been mindful of the diverse range of institutional contexts within the UK Higher Education sector and attempted to ensure that we highlight a range of positive action approaches which can be applied across that range of contexts.

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